

Anesthetic Management in A Patient with Untreated Type I Neurofibromatosis and Left Tibial Fracture: A Clinical Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Neurofibromatosis type I (NF1) is a multisystemic genetic disorder that poses significant anesthetic challenges, particularly in undiagnosed patients and emergency settings¹. This report presents the case of a male patient with cognitive disability and no prior surgical or formal NF1 diagnosis, admitted due to a distal tibial fracture². During the preoperative evaluation, clinical signs suggestive of NF1—such as café-au-lait spots, dermal neurofibromas, and Lisch nodules—were identified and confirmed by Internal Medicine³. Given a potentially difficult airway (Mallampati III, IPID 8), spinal anesthesia was chosen, using ropivacaine and fentanyl. The procedure was successful, with no hemodynamic or neurological complications⁴.

This case highlights the importance of thorough preoperative assessment and individualized anesthetic planning based on patient-specific risks⁵. It also highlights the safety of neuraxial approaches in NF1 patients when no structural contraindications are evident. This experience contributes to the medical literature by documenting a safe and effective alternative in scenarios with diagnostic uncertainty and elevated anesthetic risk.

KEYWORDS: difficult airway, spinal anesthesia, subarachnoid block, Neurofibromatosis type I.

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INTRODUCTION

Neurofibromatosis type 1 (NF1) is an autosomal dominant genetic disease caused by a mutation of the NF1 gene on chromosome 17q11.2, which produces a neurofibromin deficiency and a predisposition to the formation of ectodermal tumors. The clinical presentation mainly includes café-au-lait spots, cutaneous neurofibromas, and Lisch nodules, with possible neurological, cardiovascular, and bone abnormalities that are relevant in the perioperative period.³ NF1 presents significant anesthetic challenges due to the risk of difficult airway management secondary to intraoral or adjacent neurofibromas, as well as vascular anomalies with the potential for rupture.⁴ Perioperative cardiovascular and neurological complications related to intraspinal neurofibromas have been described, which may

contraindicate neuraxial techniques or increase the risk of epidural hematoma or nerve injury from puncture.⁵ Literature documents the safety and feasibility of neuraxial anesthesia with a favorable cardiotoxicity profile, particularly with the use of ropivacaine at appropriate doses when there are no clear structural contraindications.⁶

Study objective: To analyze the safety and effectiveness of subarachnoid block with ropivacaine in the anesthetic management of urgent orthopedic surgery (tibial fracture) in an adult patient with incidental clinical diagnosis of NF1 and assessment suggestive of a difficult airway, documenting hemodynamic stability and absence of perioperative neurological or respiratory complications as safety indicators.⁸

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Descriptive and retrospective clinical case report, analyzed using a positivist approach, focused on systematic clinical observation, anesthetic decisions and perioperative outcomes in urgent orthopedic surgery.

The population is an adult patient treated at the General Hospital of Cancun, undergoing open reduction and internal fixation of a distal tibial fracture. He is a male of 63 kg, 1.60 m, BMI 24.6 kg/m² and body surface area 1.56 m², with cognitive, language and hearing impairment since birth, without prior anesthetic exposure or specialized medical follow-up.

Clinical assessment identified incidental diagnostic signs compatible with NF1: ≥ 6 hyperpigmented "café au lait" macules (picture 1), multiple disseminated dermal neurofibromas (neck, lumbar region, groin) (picture 2) and Lisch nodules in the iris (picture 3), confirmed by the treating service. A difficult airway was anticipated (Mallampati III, IPID 8 points), without clinical signs of spinal cord compression, neuromotor deficit, active respiratory compromise or cardiovascular instability, so he was considered suitable for neuraxial anesthesia under close monitoring

Preoperative evaluation (basic perioperative panel)

Complete blood count: Hb 12.0–12.8 g/dL; leukocytes $8.1 \times 10^9/L$; platelets $386\text{--}458 \times 10^9/L$. Coagulation: PT 11.9 s; INR 1.05; aPTT 33.7 s, no evidence of coagulopathy. Additional studies: ECG with sinus rhythm 80 bpm, normal axis, no ischemia; chest X-ray without relevant findings to contraindicate regional technique.

Anesthetic technique and drugs

A subarachnoid block was performed at the L3–L4 level, with the patient seated, under strict aseptic technique, using a 25G Whitacre needle. Clear cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) return was achieved on the first attempt, with the target sensory level being T8–T10 for distal tibial surgery. The following were administered: Ropivacaine 11.5 mg, 0.75% solution, intrathecally, approximately 1.5 mL; Fentanyl 25 μg intrathecally as an adjunct (0.5 mL) to optimize analgesia.

Neuromuscular relaxants were not used to avoid unpredictable response in NF1.

Monitoring and analysis

Standard monitoring: continuous SpO₂, 3-lead ECG, cyclic non-invasive blood pressure every 3–5 min, post-puncture neurological monitoring, and hemodynamic stability. Safety and effectiveness analysis was performed using a descriptive clinical narrative approach, without comparative inference.

The protocol was approved by the hospital's Local Ethics and Research Committee (registry CEI 2025-034-HGC). Written informed consent was obtained through a family member as an intermediary; confidentiality was guaranteed through alphanumeric coding of the records and compliance with NOM-004-SSA3-2012. The research was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

RESULTS

Adequate surgical anesthesia was achieved via subarachnoid block, establishing the planned T8–T10 sensory level, with no evidence of block failure, conversion to general anesthesia, or need for advanced airway rescue devices. The patient remained hemodynamically stable throughout the intraoperative period, without hypo- or hypertension, arrhythmias, desaturation, bronchospasm, or bleeding related to the neuraxial puncture. There were no new neurological complications in the immediate postanesthetic period or during hospital recovery, including no motor impairment, neuropathy, disabling headache, or persistent sensory deficit.

DISCUSSION

This case confirms that neuraxial anesthesia can be safe and feasible in NF1 when there are no clinical signs of spinal cord compression, mediastinal masses, or coagulopathy that contraindicate its use, aligning with previous reports describing favorable outcomes with ropivacaine due to lower cardiotoxicity compared to bupivacaine. In our patient, the prediction of a difficult airway emphasized the need to minimize manipulation. The choice of ropivacaine 11.5 mg + intrathecal NF1 25 μg met the study objective: to provide effective anesthetic conditions without cardiovascular instability or new neurological complications.

A relevant limitation compared to ideal standards is the absence of spinal neuroimaging (MRI) prior to the block, a theoretical risk described in NF1; however, the favorable clinical evolution suggests that rigorous clinical assessment can safely guide decision-making in emergencies, provided that the context does not allow for advanced studies.

CONCLUSIONS

Subarachnoid block with ropivacaine proved to be an effective and hemodynamically stable anesthetic strategy in urgent orthopedic surgery in a patient with incidentally detected NF1 and a high prediction of a difficult airway, avoiding the risks of induction and intubation with uncertain rescue outcomes. The absence of new neurological complications or adverse hemodynamic events supports its viability when clinical evaluation rules out obvious contraindications for neuraxis. This report emphasizes the importance of comprehensive pre-anesthetic evaluation, early phenotypic recognition in the emergency department, and the exclusive use of generic drugs as a foundation for safety.

The findings support that, in selected contexts and under close monitoring, intrathecal regional anesthesia with ropivacaine is a safe, useful, and replicable alternative for patients with previously undiagnosed NF1.

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Pictures

Picture 1: Skin lesions and café au lait spots suggestive of neurofibromatosis type I.

Picture 2: Dermal nodular or papular lesions and coffee-colored macules (café au lait spots) of varying size and distribution.

Picture 3; Lisch nodules (iris hamartomas)